

MODERN THERAPY OF VARICOTHROMBOPHLEBITIS: BIOFLAVANOID AND ORAL THROMBOLYTIC**Poseryaev A.,***State Healthcare Institution Ulyanovsk State Clinical Hospital, Ulyanovsk, Russian Federation***Krivoschekov E.,**

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of the Ministry of Healthcare of the Russian Federation***Yashkov M.***State Healthcare Institution Ulyanovsk State Clinical Hospital, Ulyanovsk, Russian Federation***Abstract**

The paper analyzes the results of treatment of 82 patients with acute varicothrombophlebitis of the lower extremities. Conducting a comprehensive clinical and instrumental examination of patients allowed in all cases to finally establish the diagnosis and choose the optimal treatment method. The article compares the effectiveness of the use of micronized purified flavonoid fraction in comparison with synthetic analogues in groups of patients at the outpatient stage.

Keywords: thrombophlebitis, MOFF, thrombolytic, anticoagulant.

Relevance. Acute varicothrombophlebitis (OVTF) or superficial varicothrombophlebitis (TFPV) is one of the most common acute diseases of the vascular system of a vascular surgeon on an outpatient basis in clinical practice. This disease occurs 10 times more often than thrombophlebitis of non-varicose veins, and in most cases in patients suffering from varicose veins of the lower extremities for a long time [1]. The frequency of occurrence of this pathology is due to the wide prevalence of varicose veins of the lower extremities, which is observed in 80-90% of patients with subcutaneous vein thrombosis [2]. In a European population study conducted by E. Rabe et al. (2003), subcutaneous vein thrombophlebitis was diagnosed in 10-20% of patients suffering from varicose veins [1].

The importance of subcutaneous vein thrombophlebitis is due to the significant threat to the life of patients, which is associated with the spread of thrombosis from the superficial venous system to the deep veins and the possibility of pulmonary embolism. According to a number of authors, deep vein thrombosis in subcutaneous vein thrombophlebitis occurs in 3-20% of patients [3, 4, 5], and the incidence of symptomatic pulmonary embolism is in 1.9-13.3% of patients [6].

Patients with low and moderate risk of thromboembolic complications are treated conservatively, on an outpatient basis. This cohort of patients is supposed to perform radical intervention in the absence of contraindications after the relief of an acute inflammatory reaction.

The purpose of this study was to study the effectiveness of the results of treatment of patients with superficial varicothrombophlebitis in outpatient surgical practice.

Materials and methods. A prospective analysis of the case histories of outpatient patients with TFPV who were treated in 2020-2022 on the basis of the polyclinic department of the Ulyanovsk Regional Clinical Hospital by a vascular surgeon was carried out. A total of 82 patients were treated, the average age was 54.8 years. There were slightly more women than men – 49 (59.7%) and 33 (40.3%), respectively. At the initial

emergency admission, all patients underwent a standard clinical and laboratory examination, which included a general blood test, coagulogram, lung radiography, as well as ultrasound duplex scanning (USDS) of the veins and arteries of the lower extremities.

All patients were prescribed basic therapy according to clinical recommendations: Rivaroxaban (Xarelto) 10 mg once a day for 45 days, permanent elastic compression of both lower extremities of class 2, local ointment dressings with heparin-containing agents (Lyoton-1000 gel), venotonics. In addition, in order to stop the process as soon as possible, as well as accelerate recanalization, patients are prescribed a direct oral thrombolytic – Trombavazim at a dosage of 800 mg 2 times a day, a course for 21 days. The patients were divided into two groups of similar composition. The main group of the study included 44 patients, including 32 women (68.2%) and 14 men (31.8%). The comparison group consisted of 38 people, men and women equally, 19 patients each. In the main treatment group, a venotonic drug was used consisting of naturally obtained diosmin 900 mg (90%) and flavonoids in terms of hesperidin 100 mg (10%) in the form of a micronized purified flavonoid fraction (MOFF) – Detralex 1000 mg. In the comparison group, a drug was used as a venotonic, which included only diosmin in a dosage of 600 mg (Phlebopha).

Results. In a clinical study and after USDS, it was found that TFPV was more often localized in the basin of the great saphenous vein (BPV) – 47 patients (57.3%). In the system of the small subcutaneous vein (MPV), a pathological thrombotic process was detected in 26 patients (31.7%). In 9 people (11.0%), TFPV was detected in the anterior femoral tributary of the great saphenous vein, which can be considered a major vein, according to

Varicose veins were present for a long time in all patients, the distribution of classes of CVD was as follows: C2 – 25 patients (30.5%), C3 – 32 patients (39.0%), C4 – 17 patients (20.7%), C5 – 8 people (9.8%).

At the control examination, the progression of the thrombotic process was not detected in any patient in both study groups. One patient of the main study group and two people of the comparison group noted the appearance of minor bleeding during 30 days of treatment, while the patient of the main group noted the appearance of nosebleeds on the 20th day of therapy, and the man and woman of the comparison group noted the development of minor hemorrhoidal bleeding and hyperpolymenorrhea on the 27th and 12th days of treatment, respectively. These pathological conditions did not require medical treatment and were treated independently.

Complete relief of subjective clinical manifestations of varicothrombophlebitis, such as a feeling of tightness under the skin, local soreness in the area of varicose veins was noted by 34 people (77.3%) of the main group, and 22 patients (57.9%) of the comparison group. At the same time, 10 patients (22.7%) of the main group and 16 (42.1%) of the comparison group noted moderate retention of subjective symptoms at the control examination. A decrease in the signs of chronic venous insufficiency was noted in 28 people (63.6%) of the main study group and 10 (26.3%) patients of the comparison group.

According to ultrasound data, complete recanalization of initially thrombosed subcutaneous veins was observed in 31 (70.5%) patients of the main group and in 23 (60.5%) patients of the comparison group. Partial recanalization was detected in 13 (29.5%) and 15 (39.5%) patients of the main group and the comparison group, respectively.

In the patients of the main group of the study, there was a significant improvement in the indicators of nine scales according to the SF-36 quality of life questionnaire compared with the patients of the comparison group: physical functioning by 10.2%, role functioning due to physical condition by 8.8%, pain intensity decreased by 16.5%, general health improved by 5.3%, vital activity increased by 10.4%, social functioning – by 15.6%, role-based functioning due to emotional state – by 9.9%. Cumulative indicators on the scales, such as mental health and the physical component of health, were higher by 10.5% and 8.9%, respectively, in the main study group.

Conclusion. Real clinical practice demonstrates conservative tactics in the treatment of acute varicothrombophlebitis, as a method that effectively prevents the development of venous thromboembolic complications. At the same time, the use of a direct oral anticoagulant in combination with a direct oral fibrinolytic shows high efficiency in recanalization of the veins affected by the thrombotic process. Among the huge arsenal of drugs used to treat chronic venous diseases and varicothrombophlebitis in particular, the first-choice drug with proven clinical effects is MOFF (Detralex). Due to the pleiotropy of the effects and increased bioavailability due to the micronization of active molecules, the drug acts as a universal means of pharmacotherapy in patients with all forms and stages of chronic venous diseases and complications of varicose veins.

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